

The rice root nematode in lowland paddies in Kerala, India

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A survey of nematode parasites in the lowland rice areas of Kerala showed the rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in all regions (see map). All 104 soil samples collected at 43 sites were infested; so were the roots of rice planted in the soils. The number of nematodes ranged from 5 to 509/250 ml of soil and was as high as 450/sample of plant roots. Nematode infestation was found in lateritic loam, clayey loam, sandy, and pokkali (saline) soil types. The rice varieties Aswathi, Bharathi, Jaya, Mahoori, Triveni, and Annapoorna were infected. The nematode also infested the lowland weeds *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Fimbristylis miliasia*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. elusoides*, and *Vallisneria spiralis*.

The distribution of the rice root nematode in rice regions of Kerala, India.

Yield loss due to infection by rice root nematode in Triveni, Kerala, India.

Treatment ^a	Nematode population (no.)		Grain yield (kg/plot)	Yield loss (%)
	At planting, in 250 ml soil	At harvest In 250 ml soil In 5 g roots		
Natural field population	11	245	1.54	4.3
100 g infected rice roots added/plot	14	180	1.23	19.2
200 g infected rice roots added/plot	33	836	1.32	13.8
DBCP at 30 liters/ha	0	0	1.53	
E.D. (p=0.05)			0.20	

^a Mean of 6 replicates.

Studies of yield losses in 4-m² field microplots revealed significant reductions in final grain weight with increases in

nematode population in soil and plant roots at harvest (see table). □

Preliminary results of fertilization of upland rice in the Llanos Orientales of Colombia

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Preliminary trials were conducted to investigate the response to N, P, and K applications of upland rice in two soils of the Llanos Orientales of Colombia. Two experiments were on savanna soils (Oxisols), which are extremely acid (pH 3.9), and have low fertility and are high in exchangeable aluminum. Three experiments were on river-bottom soils (Entisols) without aluminum, with a medium-high fertility level and pH higher than 5.5.

The yields on the savanna soils were low because of low soil fertility and high aluminum toxicity, and because the rice variety planted (IR8) is susceptible to such adverse soil conditions. Yields were more than doubled by the application of 75 kg P₂O₅/ha, but no response was obtained from nitrogen (Fig. 1).

Statistical analysis of data from the river bottom experiments showed optimum yields of about 6 t/ha from application of 70 kg/ha of nitrogen on variety Cica 8 (Fig. 2).

No response to P or K was observed in these experiments because the soil

1. Response of upland rice (variety IR8) to N and P₂O₅ in Oxisols of the Llanos Orientales, Colombia. Mean of two locations.

2. Calculated yields of upland rice (variety CICA 8) with different N levels.

content was adequate, especially for K (P Bray II = 15.7 ppm; K = 0.72 meq/100 g soil).

The best method of applying nitrogen was 3 equal split applications at 30, 50,